

EVALUATING FACTORS THAT LEAD TO CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN E-WALLET SERVICES

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the factors that may lead to customer satisfaction in the E-wallet services in Malaysia. E-wallet recently introduced by the financial institution as alternative of payment method for customers. Service providers need to know the customer perceptions and find ways to maximize customer satisfaction in order to expand their market share. The study applied quantitative method where data was collected using questionnaires. 500 questionnaires distributed through google form to various social groups among students in Kuala Lumpur. 212 usable responses gathered within a 14 days of grace period given. 3 reminders sent generally to all the social groups to get more participations. The results show that three main factors that are important namely service quality, trust and brand image. Service providers may use the result of analysis in preparing their marketing and communication strategy for their acquisition campaign.

KEYWORDS : E-Wallet, Service Quality, Trust, Brand Image, Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Payment market in Malaysia has widely grown through the cashless or e-wallet payment method. The method of “going cashless” has recently gained popularity due to security concerns and crime issues, such as robbery and pickpocket. The cashless payment services industry was expected to be the fastest growing industry between 2019 and 2021, with the increase in its uptake at a compound annual growth rate of 53% by 2021, which was estimated to represent 16% of the Malaysian payment market share[1]. In particular, digital wallet was found to be the fourth most-used payment method (7%) in Malaysia[2].

High internet penetration and increasing number of smartphone users in Malaysia have encouraged more customers to make transactions using digital wallet. Numerous e-wallet applications are available in Malaysia, such as Touch 'n Go eWallet, Boost, GrabPay, PayPal, and Maybank QRPay[3]. The e-wallet payment method is adapted for the convenience of customers to make transactions. The e-wallet payment system, supported by all mobile devices, allows customers to transfer money to other customers using the online banking system and make transactions using their allocated funds in their digital wallet. Apart from making payment to merchants, the e-wallet payment system also provides other services, such as for loyalty card integration and marketing purposes.

The growing number of smartphone users for online shopping gives opportunity for businesses in the 21st century to apply e-wallet payment system according to the preferences of customers for cashless technology that continues to change and expand in the marketplace. A study reported that almost 62% of smartphone users today use smartphone to do online shopping. Online shopping via mobile devices accounted for about 47% of e-commerce transaction—such transaction was expected to increase at a compound annual growth rate of 31.4% by 2021, amounting to USD 5.6 billion[3]. Apart from international companies, there are many businesses with e-wallet license in Malaysia. The number of services that incorporate the e-wallet payment method has increased, such as for online shopping, e-hailing services, online gaming, and movie ticket booking system. This proved the dependence of customers on e-commerce in Malaysia when they make online purchase given their extensive use of mobile devices, adaptability to online transaction, and ease of use for cashless payment method.

With the support of the central bank, service providers for digital wallet have made good progress in promoting the cashless payment method, with the increasing number and value of non-bank from 1 million in 2017 to 31.1 million in 2018 and from RM 240.3 million in 2017 to RM 1.3 billion in 2018, respectively[4]. Most businesses in Malaysia, such as those in the retail, banking, and hospitality industries, have already applied the mobile payment system, such as Touch 'n Go e-Wallet, Boost, and GrabPay. Therefore, most mobile application companies in Malaysia extend their services in order to compete with their competitors. Apparently, the mobile

application industry nowadays has intense competition, which drives high switching costs considering that customers are likely to switch to the best service provider for digital wallet.

Despite the potential of the mobile payment system, its implementation among Malaysian customers has remained limited due to trust and security issues, such as online fraud and scams. Due to different post-use evaluations of users and levels of security, these companies tend to contribute to promotional campaigns to ensure customer satisfaction[5]. For example, Touch 'n Go e-Wallet and Boost enhance their promotional campaigns to attract more customers to make payment using their digital wallet by introducing rebates, cashback, and e-vouchers. Customers can claim bonus cashback after they make transaction using one of these mobile apps. This strategy attracts customers to utilise these mobile apps and serve as a marketing strategy to enhance customer satisfaction. This strategy is emphasised for customer retention and customer loyalty given the intense competition among mobile application companies[6]. It is important to evaluate post-purchase customer experience in the cashless payment services industry by identifying the factors that drive customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in order to retain existing customers and attract new customers for the sustainability of these companies in the marketplace.

2.1 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction can be defined as the overall purchase evaluation (before, during, and after purchase) from the viewpoints of customers. In other words, there can be positive and negative customer evaluations[7]. Customers are among the important stakeholders in a company due to their influence and involvement in transactions as end users[8]. In return, the company earns profits through the sales of products and services that are produced according to the needs and demands of customers as well as from customer retention that leads to customer loyalty[9]. Therefore, in order to ensure that both customers and companies benefit from these transactions, there is an art of exchange that customers and companies should apply[10]. An exchange value is when customers purchase a product or service from the company that gains profits from selling the product or service.

Customers create market demands. Businesses need to identify the needs and demands of customers with different tastes and preferences[11]. Customer demand serves as a guideline for businesses to produce products or services that can solve customer problems as well as their needs and demands, resulting in customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Satisfied and loyal customers would repeat their purchase[12]. For instance, Tesco offers customer membership through the implementation of loyalty card approach, specifically Tesco Clubcard, which helps the company to retain customers and expand its business across the country.

When customers are satisfied with the products and services, businesses achieve their goal of creating value for customers. There are many methods for businesses to achieve customer satisfaction. Businesses have to ensure the quality of the products and services offered to ensure customer satisfaction[13]. Customer-oriented services enhance customer satisfaction. When customers have good experience with the salesperson during their transaction and the salesperson displays good attitude and efficiently solve their problem, customer satisfaction is inevitably enhanced, which leads to repeat purchase[14]. For example, Innisfree provides training for all employees to ensure that they are able to provide good quality services to all customers. They should be familiar and able to explain about any products in store for the customers to decide on their purchase. Besides that, customer satisfaction can be achieved by providing products and services of good quality and value of money[15]. The quality of the products and services offered must align with the price set for customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, price conscious customers are more aware about the price of product or service, rather than the quality. Therefore, businesses need to identify their customer preference and market segment in order to enhance the level of customer satisfaction.

Ideally, it is the best that organisations can produce high-quality products, serve high quality of services, and create value, which ensure good relationships with customers. Having strong relationships with customers can develop customer loyalty that helps businesses to sustain and remain stable in the marketplace[13]. Businesses also come to gain in terms of high customer traffic and return on investment through repeat purchase. Strong engagement with customers helps businesses to create customer loyalty and customer retention. For instance, Harley Davidson maintains a strong relationship with its customers by involving them in the creation of motorbike design, resulting in customer loyalty. The company provides a website for customers to directly engage and interact with the company and give feedback and suggestions about the products[16].

In conclusion, both businesses and customers rely on one another and benefit from one another with the exchange value. Therefore, businesses should analyse customers' tastes and preferences in order to satisfy their needs and demands in order to ensure customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. In fact, their business strategies must be continuously improved to compete with their competitors and sustain themselves in the marketplace according to the dynamic and changing market trend and customer preference[17].

2.2 Service Quality

Quality represents the degree to which an entity satisfies the needs of its users [16]. With that, service quality can be defined as achieving customer expectation where the assessment conducted by a business is well-delivered and meets customer satisfaction. Service quality plays an essential role in the success of the services industry due to the intangible nature of services [18]. Providing good service quality reflects good corporate image of the business performance as well as contributes positive customer perception. There are various forms of service quality that can affect business performance that consists of productivity and efficiency of how well services are provided to customers[12].

Service quality consists of five dimensions, which are tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions of service quality are incorporated in SERVQUAL developed by[19]. The first element of service quality is tangible, which refers to different forms of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials, including the appearance of the staff. When employees concern about their appearance and ensure they always look smart and clean, customer satisfaction can be achieved[20]. Secondly, reliability refers to the capability of a business to perform accurate services according to the standard policy and regulations. Reliability helps to sustain a business in the industry when satisfied customers continue to use the service or make repeat purchase[5]. Thirdly, responsiveness is defined as the efficiency of a business in performing the services through the willingness and preparation of staff to assist customers. For example, they are able to help customers to solve their problem promptly. The fourth dimension of service quality is assurance, which is linked to the credibility of a business in ensuring the delivery of good services to gain customer confidence[21]. For example, employees have good knowledge of the products and can help customers to solve their problem. Lastly, empathy is defined as the concern of employees towards customers by paying attention and willingness to help customers to solve their problem[22].

Clearly, service quality can be a factor that influences customer satisfaction, where service quality drives customers to repeat their purchase or use the same service. The repeat purchase leads to customer loyalty[23]. High service quality can be consistently implemented in a business and great relationships with customers can be created. Through customer feedback, any dimension of services that a business lacks of can be improved. Therefore, a business needs to maintain its service quality on the right track in order to compete with its competitors and sustain in the marketplace. With that, businesses would be able to retain customers and encourage customer loyalty as well as ensure customer satisfaction[24].

2.3 Brand Image

According to Kotler (2001), brand image can be defined as one's beliefs, ideas, and impression of an object. Brand image can also be explained as customer perception towards a brand. It describes a form of image on how customers perceive a brand. Brand image is developed through customer interaction and experience before, during, and after the purchase. Customer demand drives the establishment of brand image by linking high-quality products to the brand that proposes customers with other benefits and product attributes, such as functional, symbol, and experience benefits, in the form of product design [25]. As mentioned by [26], the uniqueness of brand association is the overall mind reflection and beliefs of customers towards a particular brand with unique qualities, such as design, packaging, colour, texture, and other abstract dimension, which can differentiate the business from its competitors.

Brand image can be in the forms of logo, trademark, copyright, company design, packaging, and abstract dimension. For instance, large companies (e.g. Apple) have their own logo and copyright, where customers recognise their brand image and capabilities, resulting in positive customer perception[27]. In addition, it is also easier for customers to acknowledge the company's newly launched products or services. An established brand image gives advantage to businesses, as they are able to reduce their marketing cost. Therefore, businesses can be more cost-efficient and allocate their production funds to improvise their product and service quality, instead of promotional activities[28].

Having a strong brand image that is linked to social status and self-esteem can also lead to higher customer satisfaction and consumer confidence to make a purchase [27]. Some customers assume that owning products with high quality and good brand image can increase their status and individual self-image. For example, certain customers believe that purchasing an iPhone from the Apple company can enhance their self-esteem and social status due to the favourable perception of Apple. Its strong brand image and high-quality, advanced products make the brand unique and different with competitors.

Brand image differentiates a business from its competitors by boosting customer trust and developing their confidence towards the business performance and capability[29]. Developing a good brand image can create positive perception and feelings towards the brand. When customers favour a particular brand, it can drive their purchase intention and lead to customer retention when the brand achieves its goal to satisfy customers[30].

Hence, most businesses strive to establish their brand image in order to become the key player in the industry and to compete with their competitors.

2.4 Trust

Trust is a set of beliefs that customers perceive towards a product or service based on their purchase behaviour and experience[31]. A set of beliefs is linked to the ability of the company and customers to rely with one another due to honesty and reliability. In addition, the physical appearance of a company and customers' purchase experience contribute to customer trust. Through trust, customers believe that the company has the capability and credibility to satisfy their needs and demands[28]. Gaining customer trust leads to customer satisfaction, which benefits a business.

Moreover, trust also has substantial impact on a business because it leads to purchase intention among customers. According to [32], trust that is developed based on prior affective experience plays a crucial role in facilitating repurchase intention among customers. When trust is developed, customers feel secured and safe when they perform transactions with the business. It would lead to repeat purchase as they would continue their purchase, which benefit the business in terms of profits and strengthen its financial performance[33].

In order to gain customer trust, businesses should also be conducted ethically. All business information should be revealed without any false or misleading marketing just to attract customers. Most businesses conduct their promotional campaign unethically just to "bait" or promote their products, such as not stating the actual price or switching the price[34]. As a result, customers would feel dissatisfied, lose their trust towards such businesses, and eventually switch to their competitors who offer the same products or services. As for the case of online transaction, customers tend to choose the most secure platform for them to allocate their funds due to potential risks and fraud[35]. Digital wallet is one of the real-life examples in transaction where customers allocate their funds using the cashless payment method is crucial.

In short, gaining customer trust does not only involve producing products or services that satisfy the needs and demands of customers but also the commitment to conduct businesses ethically and consistently for customers[36]. Trust can lead to customer satisfaction through the mutually beneficial relationships between the company and customers. Trust can significantly lead to customer satisfaction that benefits the company in terms of profits through repeat purchase as well as enhance the engagement between the company and customers[26].

2.5 Price

According to [37], price is the total amount being exchanged for a customer to benefit from the purchased product or service. Price plays an important role in business, where it is one of the factors that determine a product or service[9]. Price in marketing indicates profit and revenue gained when the pricing meets customer demand. When businesses are able to identify the needs and demands of customers, customers are driven to purchase the product or service, regardless of the price set. Businesses must gain information from the analysis of the market and competitors in order to ensure that their products and services are in the right market with the right customers[38]. It is easier for businesses to set the ideal pricing and position for their products and services in the marketplace once they understand the market demand.

In business, there are two main types of pricing, which are penetration and skimming price. Businesses tend to set the price based on their financial objective, whether they want to gain profit in the short or long term[39]. Although a low price is set, a business can get high return on investment when mass production takes place due to high customer traffic. Certain products or services are set at a higher price as the production of these products or services are continuously improvised to improve their quality for customer retention and customer satisfaction. Some customers are willing to pay more for high-quality products or services [7].

For example, despite introducing a new iPhone model at a higher price, there is still a demand from Apple loyal customers due to brand and product quality that are of value of money. Moreover, certain businesses set their price to maximise their profit in the short or long term. Businesses must set appropriate price for their products and services in order to achieve their target revenue and profit and to sustain in the marketplace[40]. Therefore, it is crucial for businesses to determine their pricing objective as a guideline to identify and implement the best business strategy according to their business goals and objectives.

III. METHODOLOGY

A sample is a subset of the “target population or accessible population” in a study [41]. It refers to selected groups of elements that can be individuals, groups, or organisations. For this study, residents in the Klang Valley, specifically Kuala Lumpur and Selangor, represented the target population.

Meanwhile, sampling techniques refer to the methods used to choose the sample frame. Convenience sampling technique, which is one of the non-probability sampling techniques, was employed in this study. This sampling technique eases the researcher to approach the respondents. There are numerous potential respondents in the Klang Valley but only easily accessible respondents were conveniently sampled. As a result, a sample size of 150 respondents was gathered.

A questionnaire is a list of research or survey questions that are designed to extract specific information from the respondents. There are four basic purposes of questionnaire, which are to collect appropriate data, make data comparable and amenable for analysis, minimise bias in formulating and asking questions, and make questions engaging and varied [42]. The use of a questionnaire is a practical way to gather the required data from the targeted group[43]. The researcher can also administer these questionnaires in various forms and select the type and format of questions (e.g. open-ended and close-ended questions).

For this study, an online survey was conducted. The developed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale consists of six sections: (1) Section A focuses on the demographic information of respondents, which include gender, age, occupation, e-wallet application used by respondents; (2) Section B focuses on customer satisfaction (dependent variable); (3) Section C focuses on service quality (independent variable); (4) Section D focuses on trust (independent variable); (5) Section E focuses on brand image (independent variable); (6) Section F focuses on price (independent variable).

IV. FINDINGS

Analysis of the Research Model with the Method *Partial Least Square (PLS)*

This study uses the PLS analysis technique with the SmartPLS Program. From the results of data processing, PLS analysis can be done by evaluating the structural equation model. In this evaluation, there are two basic evaluations. *First*, evaluating the measurement model (*outer model*) to find out the validity and reliability of indicators that measure latent variables; the instrument validity and reliability test criteria in this study refer to *discriminant validity*, *convergent validity*, and *composite reliability*. *Second*, assess the *inner model* or *structural model* to see the relationship between constructs, the significance value and the *R-square* of the research model. Testing *Inner model* in PLS analysis is done through *bootstrap resampling*.

Hypothesised Research Model.

The hypothesised model is developed using SmartPLS 3.2.7 as showed in figure 4.1 below which consisted of sixty-three measured items using a 5 point Likert scale. These measured items were loaded on their respective constructs.

Figure 4. 1 Hypothesised Model of the Study

Evaluation of the Measurement Model (*Outer Model*)

Outer model or *measurement model* is an assessment of the validity and reliability of research variables. There are three criteria for assessing the *outer models* namely *discriminant validity*, *composite reliability*, and *convergent validity*. Based on the three criteria for measuring the measurement model from the results *bootstrapping* in the PLS method, testing the measurement model for each indicator that reflects the construct or latent variable can be explained as follows.

Discriminant validity

Apart from a series of assessments on reliability and validity of all the reflective items and constructs used in the study. This study finds it essential to further assess on its discriminant validity that is complementary to the prior assessments. Testing *discriminant validity* in research using score *square root of average (AVE)* to check (testing) whether the research instrument is valid in explaining or reflecting latent variables. *Discriminant validity* used is *square root of average variance extracted (√AVE)*. If the *square root of the average variance extracted (√AVE)* value of each variable is greater than the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables, the instrument variable is said to be valid discriminant.

Table 4.1 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

No	Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
1	Brand Image	0.798
2	Customer Satisfaction	0.745
3	Price	0.827
4	Service Quality	0.675
5	Trust	0.811

Test results in Table 4.1 show that the value of *average variance extracted (AVE)* are more than 0.5. According to Hair, Sarstedt, & Ringle (2017) the *average variance extracted (AVE)* of each latent construct should 0.5 or

higher. All constructs showed a satisfactory which explained more than 50% of variances of its items that ranges from 0.675 to 0.827.

Table 4. 2 Fornell Larker’s Criterion in Establishing Discriminant Validity (\sqrt{AVE})

	Brand Image	Customer Satisfaction	Price	Service Quality	Trust
Brand Image	0.894				
Customer Satisfaction	0.818	0.863			
Price	0.873	0.805	0.909		
Service Quality	0.837	0.825	0.817	0.822	
Trust	0.788	0.794	0.800	0.824	0.900

The table show that the *square root of average variance extracted* (\sqrt{AVE}) values of all variables are greater than the correlation between latent variables and other latent variables so that the instruments of each variable are valid discriminant. In compliance to the Fornell-Larker’s criterion this study is keen to report that the constructs and items used in this study had confirmed its discriminant validity.

Convergent validity

Convergent validity measures the validity of an indicator as a measure of construct, which can be seen from *outer loading*. From the value *outer loading*, it can also be interpreted as the contribution of each indicator to the latent variable. *Outer loading* of an indicator with the highest value means that the indicator is the strongest measure of the latent variable in question. More clearly follows the results of the analysis and evaluation of measurement models for each research variable.

Table 4.3 Outer Loading Each Indicator

	Brand Image	Customer Satisfaction	Price	Service Quality	Trust
BI1	0.877				
BI2	0.873				
BI3	0.919				
BI4	0.904				
CS1		0.868			
CS2		0.876			
CS3		0.875			
CS4		0.828			
CS5		0.869			
PR1			0.926		
PR2			0.934		
PR3			0.910		
PR4			0.865		
SQ1				0.838	
SQ2				0.870	
SQ3				0.782	
SQ4				0.768	
SQ5				0.846	
TR1					0.913
TR2					0.914
TR3					0.875
TR4					0.898

All indicators in each variable have value *outer loading* above 0.70, which means that the indicators are valid and able to measure latent variables.

Composite Reliability

Composite reliability tests the value *reliability* between the indicators of the construct that constitutes it. Results are *composite reliability* said to be good, if the value is above 0.70. Test results of *composite reliability* the measurement model are presented in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4 Composite Reliability of Constructs

No.	Construct	Composite Reliability
1	Brand Image	0.941
2	Customer Satisfaction	0.936
3	Price	0.950
4	Service Quality	0.912
5	Trust	0.945

Based on the test results in Table 4.4 obtained the value of composite *reliability* of all variables above 0.70. These results mean that the six latent variables analyzed have good composite reliability and it is concluded that all instruments used in this study have met the criteria or are suitable for use in the measurement of the five latent variables: brand image, customer satisfaction, price, service quality, and trust.

Testing of Inner Models and Research Hypotheses

Inner models or structural models evaluated by looking at the value coefficient path of the relationship between latent variables. From the PLS model output, structural model testing and hypotheses are performed by looking at the estimated path coefficient values and critical point values t-(t-statistics) that are significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 4.5 Path coefficients on relationship

Relationship	Original sample (β)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation STDV	T -Statistics	P-Values
Brand Image -> Customer Satisfaction	0.249	0.245	0.119	2.098	0.036
Price -> Customer Satisfaction	0.170	0.172	0.116	1.464	0.144
Service Quality -> Customer Satisfaction	0.302	0.294	0.112	2.712	0.007
Trust -> Customer Satisfaction	0.213	0.224	0.085	2.512	0.012

Based on the above table, result for path coefficients on relationship between BI (brand image) and CS (customer satisfaction) was β 0.249. The result on *t*-value and *p*-value explicated that BI has strong positive relationship on customer satisfaction where *t*-value = 2.098 and *p*-value = 0.036, hence, this had confirmed that the relationship of BI (brand image) toward CS (customer satisfaction) is significant because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05. Considering the assessment result of the path relationship of structural model had delineated that BI has positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Result for path coefficients on relationship between PR (price) and CS (customer satisfaction) was β 0.170. The following test on significant result through bootstrapping procedure showed *t*-value = 1.464 which less than cut-off of 1.96 and *p*-value = 0.144 that is more than 0.05, hence, this had confirmed that the relationship of PR (price) toward CS (customer satisfaction) is not significant. Considering the assessment result of the path relationship of structural model had delineated that PR has negative impact on customer satisfaction.

Result for path coefficients on relationship between SQ (service quality) and CS (customer satisfaction) was β 0.302. The result on *t*-value and *p*-value explicated that SQ has strong positive relationship on customer satisfaction where *t*-value = 2.712 and *p*-value = 0.007, hence, this had confirmed that the relationship of SQ (service quality) toward CS (customer satisfaction) is significant because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05. Considering the assessment result of the path relationship of structural model had delineated that SQ has positive impact on customer satisfaction.

Result for path coefficients on relationship between TR (trust) and CS (customer satisfaction) was β 0.213. The result on *t*-value and *p*-value explicated that TR has strong positive relationship on customer satisfaction where *t*-value = 2.512 and *p*-value = 0.012, hence, this had confirmed that the relationship of TR (trust) toward CS (customer satisfaction) is significant because the *t*-value more than 1.96 and *p*-value of less than 0.05. Considering the assessment result of the path relationship of structural model had delineated that TR has positive impact on customer satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of the study emphasis that customer is very much concerns on the service quality. Service providers must ensure that they maintain some service level guarantee and make it known to public about their policy. At the same time customer is very concerns about the customer services. Service providers must ensure that they are responsive and reliable. Beside that the staff on customer services must be exposed on the empathy and attentive.

The results also show that brand image is one of the factors that may lead to customer satisfaction. Brand image is actually part of the overall brand equity where the brand itself translated into many versions of how customers perceived about each or specific brand. Service provider may need to conduct brand awareness and communicate more frequently on their target market in order to create product and brand awareness.

It was also highlighted that beside service quality and brand image, trust is another important factors that may lead to customer satisfaction. Brand image and customer trust can only be gained based on customer experiences. Service providers need to ensure that they provide the best services in meeting customer expectations and eventually satisfied them.

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